

Table 1 illustrates prior work from the community with partially unstructured meshes, proving that partially structured meshes are required in many fields.

Table 1. Applications that Use Partially Unstructured Mesh

Applications	Link
Regional mantle convection	https://www.dealii.org/current/doxygen/deal.II/step_53.html
Global mantle convection (full Earth)	https://academic.oup.com/gji/article/192/3/889/809594
Earthquake hazard mitigation (mesh shown on p. 49)	https://geodynamics.org/cig/news/research-highlights/november-2020/
Cancer treatment	https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s40430-020-02760-1
Modeling of laser welding	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0017931017306919
Computer graphics	https://developer.nvidia.com/gpugems/gpugems2/part-v-image-oriented-computing/chapter-37-octree-textures-gpu
Immerso-geometric analysis (fluid dynamics)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045793020303340?dgcid=rss_sd_all
Flow in porous media (p. 18)	https://www.oden.utexas.edu/media/reports/2018/1803.pdf
Steady flow solvers (Nek5000)	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0045793019303111